

SUFFIX-CONSTRAINED CODES FOR PROGRESSIVE AND ROBUST DATA COMPRESSION: SELF-MULTIPLEXED CODES

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the issue of robust transmission of Variable Length Codes (VLCs) encoded sources over error-prone channels. A new class of codes, called self-multiplexed codes, is introduced. Their performance in terms of compression is the same as the one of classical VLCs (e.g. Huffman codes). Their property in terms of energy distribution on respective transitions of the codetree allows to confine error propagation to transitions bearing low reconstruction energy. Simulation results reveal high performances in terms of signal to noise ratio.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entropy coding, producing variable length codewords, is a core component of any data compression scheme. The main drawback of VLCs is their high sensitivity to channel noise: when some bits are altered by the channel, synchronization losses can occur at the receiver, the position of symbol boundaries are not properly estimated, leading to dramatic symbol error rates (SER). This phenomenon has motivated studies of the synchronization capability of VLCs as well as the design of codes with better synchronization properties [1]. Reversible VLCs [2] have also been designed to fight against de-synchronizations. Soft VLC decoding ideas, exploiting residual source redundancy (the so-called “excess-rate”) as well as the inter-symbol dependency, have also been shown to reduce the “de-synchronization” effect [3][4]. For a given number of source symbols, the number of bits produced by a VLC coder is a random variable. The decoding problem is then to properly segment the noisy bitstream into measures on symbols and estimate the symbols from the noisy sequence of bits (or measurements) that is received. This segmentation problem can be addressed by introducing a-priori information in the bitstream, taking often the form of synchronization patterns. This *a priori* information is then exploited as constraints by the decoding process. One can alternatively, by a proper structuring of the bitstream, reveal and exploit constraints on some bit positions. This idea is applied in [5] to blocks within an image. A structure of fixed length size slots inherently creates hard synchronization points in the bitstream. The resulting bitstream structure is called EREC (Error-Resilient Entropy Codes). Then, it appears that first transitions of VLC codetrees are mapped in a deterministic way.

The principle can however be pushed further. Thus, the design criterion that we consider is the amenability of VLCs and of transmission schemes for SNR error resilience, i.e. their signal to noise ratio (SNR) performance in presence of transmission errors. It is well known that codes with same compression efficiency may have different re-synchronizing properties. Similarly, codes with the same compression performances may have different energy concentration characteristics. Hence, VLC codetrees can be designed in such a way that most of the symbols *energy* is concentrated on transitions on the codetree corresponding to bits that will be mapped (on coder and decoder sides) in a deterministic way.

Given a classical VLC tree (e.g. a Huffman codetree), one can build a new codetree, by re-assigning symbols to leaves in order to satisfy the above criterion, leading to so-called *pseudo-lexicographic* codes. However, the amount of energy concentrated on the first layers of the tree strongly depends on the size and the structure of the alphabet. The codetree can be extended by assigning several fixed length codewords to a given symbol. A codeword can be seen as formed by a prefix representing the symbol followed by a suffix that will be used to represent subsequent symbols, hence the name *self-multiplexed* codes. These codes can also be regarded as multiplexed binary lexicographic [6] codes in the context of a unique source. The resulting compression properties of self-multiplexed codes are identical to those of classical VLCs. In contrast to *pseudo-lexicographic* codes, and similar to Fixed Length Codes (FLCs), the codeword assignment is not constrained by the tree structure. Hence, *self-multiplexed* codes provide higher degrees of freedom to optimize the signal energy concentration on the bits that will not suffer from any de-synchronization, leading in turn to higher SNR performances in presence of errors.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the problem addressed and the notations used in the sequel. Multiplexed codes are presented in section 3. A bit mapping algorithm is proposed in section 4. Expectation-based and progressive decoding properties are then considered in section 5 leading to the design of *self-multiplexed* codes (section 6). Simulation results are provided and discussed in section 7.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND NOTATIONS

Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_t, \dots, S_K)$ be a sequence of source symbols taking their values in a finite alphabet $\mathcal{A}$ composed of Ω symbols, $\mathcal{A} = \{a_1, \dots, a_i, \dots, a_\Omega\}$. In the sequel, we assume that $i_1 < i_2 \Rightarrow a_{i_1} < a_{i_2}$. Let $\mathcal{C}$ be a binary variable length code designed for this alphabet, according to its stationary probability μ . To each symbol a_i is associated a codeword $\mathcal{C}(a_i)$ denoted by $b_i = b_i^1 \dots b_i^{l_i}$, where l_i stands for the length of the codeword b_i . The term $l_t = L(S_t)$ represents the length of the codeword associated to the realization s_t of the symbol S_t . In classical compression systems, the sequence of codewords produced would be transmitted *sequentially*, forming a *concatenated* bitstream. In the sequel, the emitted bitstream is denoted $\mathbf{E} = E_1 \dots E_{K_E}$ and its realization is denoted $\mathbf{e} = e_1 \dots e_{K_E}$. The length K is assumed to be known at the time of decoding, but not necessarily K_E .

3. BINARY MULTIPLEXED CODES

A family of codes, called multiplexed codes, has been introduced in [7]. Their design principle relies on the fact that compression systems of real signals generate sources of information with different levels of priority (e.g., texture and motion information for a video signal). Two sources, a high priority source and a low priority source referred to respectively as $\mathbf{S}_H$ and $\mathbf{S}_L$, are considered. These codes are such

class $\mathcal{C}_i$	codeword	a_i	l_i	2^{c-l_i}	μ_i	$\bar{U}_i$
$\mathcal{C}_1$	000	a_1	2	2	0.30	0
	001					1
$\mathcal{C}_2$	010	a_2	1	4	0.43	10
	011					11
	100					00
	101					01
$\mathcal{C}_3$	110	a_3	3	1	0.25	$\emptyset$
$\mathcal{C}_4$	111	a_4	3	1	0.02	$\emptyset$

Table 1: $\mathcal{C}^*$: a lexicographic binary multiplexed code.

that the risk of “de-synchronization” is confined to the low priority information. The idea consists in creating a FLC for the $\mathbf{S}_H$ source, in partitioning the set of FLCs in *classes of equivalence* and in exploiting the redundancy inherent to each class to represent or store information of the low priority source $\mathbf{S}_L$. The fixed length codewords will then represent jointly a symbol of the high priority source and some data of the low priority source. If the cardinal of each equivalence class is a power of two, some bits $\bar{U}_i$ of the low priority source can be directly described by the choice of a codeword in the equivalence class. In that case, the multiplexed code is said to be a *binary multiplexed code* [6]. The choice of a particular codeword in the class $\mathcal{C}_i$ permits to represent bits $\bar{U}_i = U_i^1 \dots U_i^{c-l(a_i)}$ of the low priority source (see table 1).

A binary multiplexed code $\mathcal{C}^*$ can be constructed from a VLC code $\mathcal{C}$ by choosing the length c of the codewords of $\mathcal{C}^*$ equal to the length h_C^+ of the longest codeword of $\mathcal{C}$, i.e. $c = h_C^+$, and such that the cardinal N_i of each equivalence class $\mathcal{C}_i$ equals 2^{c-l_i} , where l_i is the length of the codeword describing a_i in $\mathcal{C}$. The amount of bits used to describe the symbol a_i in $\mathcal{C}^*$ is thus given by $c - \log_2(N_i) = l_i$. Therefore, the codes $\mathcal{C}$ and $\mathcal{C}^*$ have exactly the same compression properties. In the following, the length l_i refers to the length $l_i = c - \log_2(N_i)$ provided by the realization $s_t = a_i$ of S_t . The next step in the construction procedure is the assignment of codewords to the different equivalence classes. Several assignment strategies can be considered.

we consider an index assignment according to the lexicographical order. We consider in addition the case where the way the bits $\bar{U}_i$ index a particular codeword within an equivalence class is defined by the suffix of the codeword (the bits $\bar{U}_i$ equal the codeword suffix). The code $\mathcal{C}^*$ presented in table 1 has been designed, using this construction procedure, from the Huffman code $\mathcal{C}$ defined by $\mathcal{C}(a_1) = 10$, $\mathcal{C}(a_2) = 0$, $\mathcal{C}(a_3) = 110$ and $\mathcal{C}(a_4) = 111$.

These codes have been designed initially for robust transmission of two heterogeneous sources. that re-writing rules applied to lexicographical binary multiplexed codes lead naturally to the so-called self-multiplexed codes allowing for robust and progressive transmission of symbols of a unique source.

4. CONSTANT MAPPING ALGORITHM (CMA)

In this section, we describe a simple solution for constructing bitstreams. Given a code $\mathcal{C}$, the solution is based on the mapping of the maximum number of bits into deterministic positions. The mapping positions of these bits do not depend on the source realization, hence is *constant*. The remaining bits to be mapped are then simply concatenated.

A variable length codetree comprises a section of a fixed length equal to the minimum length of a codeword denoted h_C^- , followed by a variable length section. Let b_i^l be a bit

realization such that $l \leq h_C^-$. This bit can be allocated a bitstream position $\varphi_C(t, l)$ as

$$(t, l) \mapsto \varphi_C(t, l) = (l-1)K + t \quad (1)$$

In contrast with classical transmission schemes where the codewords are concatenated, error propagation will only take place on the tuples (t, l) such that $l > h_C^-$. This bit mapping amounts to transmitting the fixed length section of the codewords bit plane per bit plane. Hence, for a Huffman tree, the most frequent symbols will not suffer from de-synchronization. Although, for classical VLCs, the CMA algorithm is outperformed by the EREC algorithm, we will see in section 7 that this mapping is efficient when used jointly with the new class of codes, called self-multiplexed codes, described in section 6. This layered bitstream structure is well suited for unequal error protection. Note also that this scheme is amenable to soft decoding using Bayesian estimation principles.

5. PROGRESSIVE DECODING AND SNR PERFORMANCE DESIGN CRITERIA

VLC codewords can be decoded progressively by regarding the bit generated by the transitions at a given level of the codetree as a bit-plane or a layer. Progressive decoding can then be achieved by considering an expectation-based decoding approach.

5.1 Expectation-based decoding

Let us assume that the l first bits of a codeword have been received. They correspond to an internal node n_j of the codetree. Let $\mathcal{L}_j$ and $\bar{\mu}_j = \sum_{n_i \in \mathcal{L}_j} \mu_i$ respectively denote the leaves deduced from n_j and the probability associated to the node n_j . Then the optimal reconstruction value $\tilde{a}_j$ is given by

$$\tilde{a}_j = \frac{1}{\bar{\mu}_j} \sum_{n_i \in \mathcal{L}_j} \mu_i a_i \quad (2)$$

The corresponding mean square error (MSE), referred to as Δ_j , is given by the variance of the source knowing the first bits, i.e., by

$$\Delta_j = \frac{1}{\bar{\mu}_j} \sum_{n_i \in \mathcal{L}_j} \mu_i (a_i - \tilde{a}_j)^2.$$

Let us consider the codetree modelling the decoding process. The reception of one bit will trigger the transition from a parent node n_j to children nodes $n_{j'}$ and $n_{j''}$ depending on the bit realization. The corresponding reconstruction MSE is then decreased as $\Delta_j - \Delta_{j'}$ or $\Delta_j - \Delta_{j''}$ depending on the value of the bit received. Given a node n_j , the expectation δ_j of the MSE decrease for the corresponding transition T_j is given by

$$\delta_j = \Delta_j - \frac{\mu_{j'} \Delta_{j'} + \mu_{j''} \Delta_{j''}}{\mu_{j'} + \mu_{j''}}$$

The total amount δ_i^* of reconstruction energy corresponding to a given layer l of a VLC codetree can then be calculated as the weighted sum of energies given by transitions corresponding to the given layer:

$$\delta_i^* = \sum_{T_j \text{ in layer } l} \bar{\mu}_j \delta_j$$

5.2 Progressive SNR design criteria

Since the last bits of a codeword are more likely to be desynchronized, in order to maximize the SNR performance in presence of transmission errors, the code is signed so that it concentrates most of the energy on the bits (or codetree transitions) corresponding to the first layers. The code design can be expressed as the maximization of the values δ_i^* for the bit transitions of the first layers. Since the first layers (which can be regarded as *most significant* bits) bring more information than subsequent layers, codes designed according to this criterion will lead to better SNR performances in a context of progressive decoding.

Note that, if the quantities K and K_E are both known, error propagation can be detected if the termination constraints are not verified. Here, by termination constraints, we mean that the K_E bits of $\mathbf{E}$ must lead to decode K symbols of $\mathbf{S}$. In that case, it may be better to restrict the expectation based decoding to the bits that cannot be desynchronized. This approach is referred to as *truncated* in the sequel, and offers its best results if the subset of bits used for the reconstruction contains a sufficient amount of energy.

5.3 Pseudo-lexicographic (p-lex) codes

Given a classical VLC, e.g. a Huffman code, which specifies the length l_i of each symbol a_i , symbols can be re-assigned to leaves in order to best satisfy the above criterion. A new codetree can then be constructed using a bottom-up approach, leading to a so-called *pseudo-lexicographic* variable length codetree. The code construction can be summarized as follows. Starting with the bottom layer, referred to as the layer h_C^+ , the nodes (including leaves) are sorted according to their expectation value given in Eqn. 2. Pairs of nodes are grouped according to the resulting order. The corresponding parent nodes are in turn assigned their reconstruction value. The processing of the codetree continues until the codetree is fully constructed. The code constructed with this method is referred to as *p-lex* in the sequel.

6. SELF-MULTIPLEXED CODES: DESIGN AND RELATED SCHEMES

The amount of energy concentrated on the first layer depends on the properties of the alphabet $\mathcal{A}$. The alphabet, hence the codetree, can be extended by assigning several fixed length codewords to a given symbol. A codeword can then be seen as formed by a prefix representing the symbol followed by a suffix that will be used to represent subsequent symbols, hence the name *self-multiplexed* codes. In contrast with the *pseudo-lexicographic* codes, and similarly to FLCs, the codeword assignment, being not constrained by the tree structure, leads to the best concentration of signal energy, hence to a reduced reconstruction MSE for the first layers.

Self-multiplexed codes can thus be regarded as lexicographic binary multiplexed codes in the particular case of a unique source. In binary multiplexed codes, as explained in section 3, the codewords of a given equivalence class $\mathcal{C}_i$ represent the same symbol a_i of the high priority source. Instead of describing some data of a low priority source, the suffix is used to describe codewords of subsequent symbols.

6.1 Self-multiplexed encoding and decoding with a concatenated mapping

On the encoder side, the choice of a codeword representing a given symbol S_t is constrained by the suffix, which must correspond to the first bits of the next codeword(s). The suffix length to be used is given by $c - l_t$. As a consequence, the sequence must be encoded backward (from the last to the first symbol). The encoding process consists in selecting

t	s_t	cwd	e_1	e_2	e_3	e_4	e_5	e_6	e_7	e_8	e_9	e_{10}	e_{11}	e_{12}	e_{13}
8	a_2	100													1
7	a_1	001											0	0	
6	a_1	000									0	0			
5	a_2	100							1						
4	a_3	110					1	1	0						
3	a_2	011			0										
2	a_2	101			1										
1	a_1	001	0	0											

Table 2: Example 1: self-multiplexed codes with concatenated transmission scheme

the codeword describing the targeted symbol which verifies the suffix constraint. For the last symbol, a suffix constraint may not exist. In that case, the suffix constraint is arbitrarily assumed to be a sequence of 0's, identified in the following example with zeros in italic.

Example 1: Let $\mathcal{A} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$ be the alphabet of the source $\mathbf{S}$ with the stationary probabilities given by $\mu_1 = 0.30$, $\mu_2 = 0.43$, $\mu_3 = 0.25$ and $\mu_4 = 0.02$. Let $\mathbf{s} = a_1 a_2 a_2 a_3 a_2 a_1 a_1 a_2$ be a given realization of the source $\mathbf{S}$. With the code $\mathcal{C}^*$ of table 1, the emitted bitstream $\mathbf{e} = e_1 e_2 \dots e_{K_E}$ is constructed as shown in table 2.

The sequence of bits received is decoded from the first bit to the last bit as follows: c bits of the bitstream are read, identifying the symbol S_t to be decoded and its length l_t . A bitstream pointer (initialized on the first position) is then incremented by l_t bitstream positions (and not c). Thus the last $c - l_t$ bits are re-used for decoding the following symbols.

6.2 Link with Rewriting Rules

Formally, the encoding of self-multiplexed codes using the concatenation of codewords can also be seen as a rewriting system of the sequence $\mathbf{S}$ using production rules (implicitly defined by the code) of the form

$$a_i \overline{U}_i \rightarrow \text{codeword},$$

For example, the code of table 1 amounts to define the following rewriting rules.

$$\begin{array}{ll} a_1 0 & \rightarrow 000 \\ a_2 10 & \rightarrow 010 \\ a_2 00 & \rightarrow 100 \\ a_3 & \rightarrow 110 \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{ll} a_1 1 & \rightarrow 001 \\ a_2 11 & \rightarrow 011 \\ a_2 01 & \rightarrow 101 \\ a_4 & \rightarrow 111 \end{array}$$

Specific starting rules (for the last symbols of the sequences), are used if the last symbol is not sufficient to trigger a production rule by itself. They can be defined by assuming that missing bit(s) equal 0. Then, the production rules can be applied. The purpose of these rules is to transform the sequence $\mathbf{s}$ into the sequence $\mathbf{e}$ of bits. Any segment of the current sequence (composed of symbols *and* bits, initialized by $\mathbf{s}$) can be rewritten if there exists a rule having this segment as an input (this input is composed of one symbol *and* a variable number of bits). When the production rules stop, the sequence contains only bit entities. On the decoder side, the decoding can be processed forward using reverse rules, e.g. $000 \rightarrow a_1 0$. This formalism can be somewhat related to the grammar codes, recently analyzed in [8]. To the best of our knowledge, this kind of codes has never been studied in the context of error resilient source coding.

6.3 Self-multiplexed encoding and decoding with the CMA

In order to use the CMA algorithm jointly with self-multiplexed codes, the backward encoding procedure pre-

t	s_t	cwd	e_1	e_2	e_3	e_4	e_5	e_6	e_7	e_8	e_9	e_{10}	e_{11}	e_{12}	e_{13}
8	a_2	100								1					
7	a_1	000							0						0
6	a_1	000						0							0
5	a_2	100					1								
4	a_3	110			1						1	0			
3	a_2	010		0											
2	a_2	010	0												
1	a_1	001	0								0				

Table 3: Example 2: Self-multiplexed codes with CMA

sented above must be slightly modified. The algorithm proceeds symbol per symbol starting from the last symbol in the sequence. The suffix constraint that will lead to the selection of the codeword for the next symbol to be processed is given only by the bits of the remaining (i.e. variable) part of the previous codewords. The first h_c^- bits of the selected codeword are then mapped in bitstream positions e_i given by Eqn. 1. The remaining bits of this codeword are concatenated, as shown in table 3.

The decoding proceeds with first extracting h_c^- bits from the bitstream *constant* section. The variable part of the codeword is processed by extracting $c - h_c^-$ bits from the bitstream *variable* segment. These c bits allow to identify the codeword and its length l_t , leading to process the suffix constraint given by the last $c - L(S_t)$ bits. The bits of the suffix constraint are then re-used to decode the following symbols. Practically, a bitstream pointer, starting at the first position of the *variable* segment, is incremented by $L(S_t) - h_c^-$ positions.

6.4 Localization of source energy

For all these codes, one can calculate the reconstruction energy δ_l^* provided by a given layer l , as explained in section 5. For example, for the Huffman code $\mathcal{C}$ introduced in section 3, the reconstruction energy corresponding to the layers is given by $\delta_1^* = 0.0019$, $\delta_2^* = 15.2827$ and $\delta_3^* = 0.4630$. The corresponding self-multiplexed code $\mathcal{C}^*$ of table 1 leads to the values $\delta_1^* = 8.70148$, $\delta_2^* = 6.5831$ and $\delta_3^* = 0.4630$. This result illustrates the amenability of self-multiplexed codes to concentrate most of the reconstruction energy on the first bit transitions. Self-multiplexed codes by themselves (i.e. with classical concatenated mapping) do not lead *a priori* to improved error resilience. However, we will see in section when used jointly with a constant bitstream mapping, these codes allow to guarantee, in presence of transmission errors, hard synchronization of most of the signal *ene* SNR performances in presence of transmission errors) and at the same time they offer best progressivity characteristics.

7. SIMULATION RESULTS

The performances of the different codes and bitstream construction algorithms have been evaluated in terms of SNR with a Gaussian source of zero-mean and standard deviation $\sigma = 1$, uniformly quantized on 8 cells partitioning the interval $[-3, +3]$. The results shown are averaged over 1000 channel and source realizations of 200 symbols. The channel is a binary symmetrical channel (BSC).

The set of experiments aimed at comparing the proposed scheme with the concatenated scheme and a solution based on EREC [5] applied on a symbol (or codeword) basis, for channel error rates going from 10^{-4} to 10^{-1} . In presence of transmission errors, the SNR obtained with the pseudo-lexicographic and self-multiplexed codes with and without bitstream truncation (the truncated segment corresponds to the segment mapped with deterministic positions only) are shown in Fig.1. The truncation is

Figure 1: SNR performances of proposed schemes.

applied only if the termination constraint is not verified as explained in section 5. It can be observed that, in presence of transmission errors, the self-multiplexed codes outperform significantly (in terms of SNR) the p-lex Huffman codes used with the EREC algorithm. The results confirm that error propagation affects a smaller amount of reconstruction energy.

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new class of codes, called *self-multiplexed* codes, has been introduced. These codes can be regarded as a form of lexicographic binary multiplexed codes for a unique source. They have the same compression properties as classical VLCs and can be designed to reveal interesting energy distribution properties, allowing to map most of the reconstruction energy in deterministic bitstream positions. These codes turn out to offer very advantageous features: low cost coding and decoding processes, high compression efficiency (as good as Huffman codes), with high SNR performances in presence of transmission noise. They are in addition well suited for progressive decoding.

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